

Il Viaggio di Marco Polo da Tabriz a Xanadu

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Politecnico di Torino

Abstract: In quattro discussioni precedenti, e seguendo quanto riportato nel Milione, abbiamo studiato alcune parti del viaggio di Marco Polo che ha portato il veneziano fino alla corte di Kublai Khan a Xanadu. Ora presentiamo il tragitto completo da Tabriz in Persia a Xanadu, residenza estiva del Khan. Un ulteriore itinerario da Pechino a Xanadu sarà riproposto.

Keywords: Satellite Images, Google Earth, Wikimapia, Marco Polo, Milione.

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Il "Milione" è un libro del tredicesimo secolo, scritto da Rustichello da Pisa. Nel libro, Rustichello riporta le storie ed i viaggi che Marco Polo gli raccontò mentre erano insieme prigionieri a Genova. Il libro racconta anche del lungo periodo che Marco Polo trascorse alla corte di Kublai Khan [1]. Una versione in Inglese del Milione è stata proposta da Sir Henry Yule (1820–1889), disponibile al link https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/The_Travels_of_Marco_Polo.

Circa i viaggi di Marco Polo, in alcune discussioni precedenti abbiamo mostrato quattro itinerari. In [2], si è proposto un itinerario da Tabriz, in Persia, fino a Sapurgan (oggi Shibargan o Sheberghan. In Afghanistan). Da questo posto, in [3], si passa a Cascar, l'oasi-città di Kashgar nello Xinjiang. Si è proposto un possibile itinerario attraverso le montagne del Pamir, seguendo le parole di Marco Polo e le vie, i fiumi e i laghi che possiamo vedere in Google Earth. In [4], c'è l'itinerario da Kashgar a Xanadu. Infine, in [5], si era proposto un itinerario per Xanadu, la

capitale estiva di Kublai Khan, da Pechino, la capitale invernale dell'impero Yuan.

Seguendo il percorso completo, esso appare un percorso possibile, che i mercanti veneziani potrebbero aver seguito con la necessità di finanziare il viaggio stesso.

In passato, ci sono stati dei ricercatori che hanno esposto dei dubbi sul reale viaggio di Marco Polo. Ecco, a questo proposito, alcune considerazioni proposte in [6]. In [6] si cita Francis Wood, direttrice del Dipartimento di Studi Cinesi della British Library, che ha pubblicato nel 1995 un libro intitolato "Marco Polo è andato in Cina?" [si veda anche [7]]. Il libro suscitò scalpore in quanto contraddiceva la tradizione secondo la quale Marco Polo fosse giunto effettivamente in Estremo Oriente. Secondo la Wood, Marco Polo non sarebbe mai andato oltre il Mar Nero. I dubbi nascerebbero poiché Marco Polo non avrebbe trattato alcune questioni che, "a parere dell'autrice, non potevano non essere menzionate, quali la Grande Muraglia, la tradizione del te', l'uso delle bacchette per mangiare, per non parlare della mancata presenza del viaggiatore italiano negli archivi ufficiali cinesi dell'epoca" [6].

Spiega [6] che l'idea che Marco Polo non fosse giunto in Cina non era del tutto nuova. Uno dei punti principali su cui si basa la tesi del libro della Wood e dei altri lavori di studiosi che non credono nel viaggio del veneziano è che esso appare geograficamente incoerente, "sia dal punto di vista dell'itinerario che da quello cronologico" [6]. Il sito [6] espone poi gli altri vari dubbi sul Milione, ma dice anche che tali "affascinanti dubbi sollevati dalla Wood, sono stati ampiamente criticati, confutati e smontati da molti storici cinesi, come Fang Hao o Yang Zhijiu, e di altre nazionalità, che si sono basati non sulle mancanze, in fin dei conti Marco Polo non stava scrivendo la Lonely Planet sulla Cina, ma sulle sue dettagliate descrizioni dei luoghi da lui visitati, e su altre prove. Nel 1997 Igor de Rachewiltz [si veda [8]], stimato docente universitario romano di origine polacche, ha analizzato e smantellato punto per punto le tesi revisioniste, nel suo articolo "Marco Polo è andato in Cina" pubblicato in Zentralasiatische Studien".

Per quanto riguarda l'itinerario da Tabriz a Xanadu e quello da Pechino a Xanadu, non è vero che sono incoerenti. Essi appaiono del tutto coerenti, tanto che oggi possiamo seguirli agilmente su Google Earth. Di seguito si trovano le discussioni [2]-[5].

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Marco Polo in Persia

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Politecnico di Torino

Abstract: In three previous discussions, we investigated the travels of Marco Polo, with the help of Google Earth and Wikimapia. We reconstructed Polo's travels from Beijing to Xanadu, from Sheberghan to Kashgar, and from Kashgar to Xanadu. Here we propose Polo's travel in Persia. The place of a Mulehet Castle, close to Ferdows in the Tunocain county, is also evidenced. It is possible that Marco Polo was referring to this castle, the Ghal'eh Kuh of Ferdows, when he was reporting about the Old Man of the Mountain, and not to the Alamut Castle in the South Caspian province of Qazvin.

Keywords: Satellite Images, Google Earth, Wikimapia, Marco Polo, Persia.

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The "Milione" is a book of the thirteenth century, written by Rustichello da Pisa. In it, Rustichello reported the stories and travels that Marco Polo told him while they were both prisoners in Genoa. The book also tells of the period that Marco Polo spent at the court of Kublai Khan [1]. An English version of Milione is that written by Sir Henry Yule (1820–1889), available at the link https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/The_Travels_of_Marco_Polo.

About Polo's travels in some previous articles we have discussed three routes. In [2], we have proposed the itinerary to Xanadu, the summer capital of Kublai Khan, from Beijing, the winter capital of the Yuan empire. The results were so encouraging that our study continued. In [3], we followed the journey from Sapurgan, today Sheberghan in Afghanistan, to Cascar, the oasis city of Kashgar in Xinjiang. In particular, a possible route through Pamir mountains has been proposed, following the words of Marco Polo and the roads, rivers and lakes that we can see in Google Earth. In [4], the itinerary from Kashgar to Xanadu was followed. We used, to find the places named by Polo, Google Earth and Wikimapia.

Now, let's read Polo's Milione [1] again, to find possible routes followed by the Venetian in Persia. Polo first talks about the countries of modern Turkey and Iraq, and then he moves on to Persia. Besides the routes, in the following discussion the place of a Mulehet Castle, close to Ferdows in the Tunocain county, will be also evidenced. It is possible that Marco Polo was referring to this castle, the Ghal'eh Kuh of Ferdows, when he was reporting about the Old Man of the Mountain, and not to the Alamut Castle in the South Caspian province of Qazvin.

... Let us leave from Toris (Tabriz) and enter Persia ([1], page 69). In Persia, there is Sava the town from which the three Magi started their travel. Marco seeks information about them in Cala (Qala = castle) Ataperistan (of the fire worshipers). He says that Persia has eight kingdoms: Casvin, Kurdistan, Lor, Sulistan, Isfaan, Serazi, Soncara, Tunocain. Marco Polo then tells of Jasdi (page 73). After seven days of travel we enter the kingdom of Cherman. ...

Many thanks to Google Earth for the maps that are here used for study and research.

Figure 1: From Toris (Tabriz), let us move to Jasdi (Yazdi), passing through Sava (Saveh). In Internet, we find told that the castle of the Old Man of the Mountain, to which Marco Polo was referring, was Alamut castle in the South Caspian province of Qazvin. Therefore this should be the district Mulete, Mulehet, but in [1] it is said that this district has not been identified. Here in the following, let us read what the Enciclopedia Iranica is telling about, <https://iranicaonline.org/articles/polo-marco> - "Various chapters of the Description of the World are dedicated to the the Viel de la Montaigne/Veglio della Montagna, "the Old Man of the

Mountain,” the šayḡ al-jabal of the Islamic sources (Polo, 1938, I, pp. 128-32; 1975, sec. 39-42; 1999, pp. 138-40; 2001, pp. 166-69; Nowell 1947), Alaodin (‘Alā-al-Din Moḡammad) who was the seventh Grand Master of the Isma‘ilis of Alamut called Assassins/Assassini/Harcassis/Hasisins, a term probably derived by the word ḡašīš/ḡašīšiyin, although this etymology remains controversial (Pelliot, 1959-73, I, pp. 52-55). The country of the members of the sect is called Milect/Mulect/Mulehet/Milice, a corruption of the word molḡed “heretic,” mistakenly applied by Marco Polo to the region (Pelliot, 1959-73, II, pp. 785-87). The description given by Marco Polo of the marvelous garden where ‘Alā-al-Din Moḡammad and the Isma‘ilis lived, and of the activities of the Grand Master, are practically identical with those of Oderico da Pordenone (Wyngaert, 1929, pp. 488-89). Polo also describes the destruction of Alamut by Hulagu”.

<http://archive.is/A3KJI>

Leaving the town of Cherman, you have to ride for seven days, moving in a beautiful land with towns and villages. You reach a very high mountain, from which the route descends for two days. Then you arrive to a vast land where there is Camadi, in the Reobar (Jirufti) region. The region was infested with brigands, who took Marco. He managed to escape and found asylum in the Canosalmi castle (Pag. 77). After crossing a flat land you came to another descent to the land of Cormosa (Hormutz).

Many thanks to Google Earth for the maps that are here used for study and research.

Figure 2: From Jasdi, we can arrive to Cherman. Then we can move to Camadi (Jiroft), and then to Cormosa (Hormuz). Marco Polo told that he moves back from Carmose, following another route, and therefore we

followed another itinerary too. Let us read again the Enciclopedia Iranica about Camadi. "The village of Camadi or Camandi (Qamādin), a suburb near Jiroft, in the realm of Reobales (Rudbār?), was famous for dates and other fruits (Pelliot, 1959-73, I, p. 139), and it was here that animals such as donkeys and rams with their typical fat tails could be found. The local population built walls of earth to defend themselves.

They sold slaves and were under King Nogodar, identified as a chief of the Carans/ Carans/ Charaunas/Caraonas /Scherani, the Qaraunas (Pelliot, 1959-73, I, pp. 183-96; II, p. 792) about whom Marco Polo gives information in various parts of his text (Polo, 1928, sec. XXXVI; 1938, I, pp. 120-22; 1975, sec. 8, 35, 114-15; 2001, pp. 158-59; see also Aubin, 1969). To escape from them Marco Polo takes refuge in the castle of Canosalmi/Ganasalim (probably *Qanāt-e Šāh: Pelliot, 1959-73, I, p. 158)." <http://archive.is/A3KJI>

We return to tramontana (the north wind) by another route to Cherman (page 79). We arrive at Cobinan (page 81). Then we pass a desert and arrive at the province of Tunocain. There is a large flat land where there is the Albero Solo (the tree of Alexander the Great). Polo then reports of the Mulete region and of the Veglio della Montagna. Then, he resumed the description of the travel: for six days the traveler meets some deserts and then arrives in Sapurgan (Shibargan, Sheberghan) in Afghanistan.

Many thanks to Google Earth for the maps that are here used for study and research.

Figure 3: From Cobinan to Shibargan, this is the most difficult route to determine. Marco Polo tells that he

crossed the district of Tunocain. The name is thought to come from the union of the names of two towns, Toon (Tun) and Qa'en. Toon is today's Ferdows. Near Ferdows there are the ruins of a very important fortress (Kuh-e-Ghal'eh). In my opinion, this could be the fortress of the Mulehet district described by Polo, and not that near the Caspian Sea. I am telling this, because the description of the fortress of the Old Man of the Mountain is made just when Marco describes the road from Tunocain to Shibargan. Wikipedia gives information us about the fortress. "Ghal'eh Kuh of Ferdows is a ruined fortress on top of Kuh-e Ghal'eh , located south of Ferdows (Tun) in South Khorasan Province, Iran. The fortress was famously used by the Nizari Ismailis of the Alamut period, and was the biggest Nizari stronghold in the Quhistan region, according to the Tarikh-i Jahangushay. [1] It was connected to the nearby Ghal'eh Kuh of Hasanabad (also known as Ghal'eh Dokhtar) and to the city of Tun itself via secret tunnels discovered after the 1968 Dasht-e Bayaz and Ferdows earthquakes.[2][3] The fortress was destroyed and burned in May 1256 after its capture by the invading Mongols under Kitbuqa and Köke Ilgei [4][5]". <http://archive.is/tk7Eu>

Marco Polo doesn't provide detailed information about his route to Shibargan. We can imagine that he arrived in Razav and then went down to Herat, without reaching the town. Herat, which had fallen under the rule of the Mongols, was destroyed before the arrival of Marco Polo in Persia. Wikipedia tells that "Herat was invaded and destroyed by Genghis Khan's Mongol army in 1221. The city was destroyed a second time and remained in ruins from 1222 to about 1236. In 1244 a local prince Shams al-Din Kart was named ruler of Herāt by the Mongol governor of Khorāsān and in 1255 he was confirmed in his rule by the founder of the Il-Khan dynasty Hulagu. Shams al-Din founded a new dynasty and his successors, especially Fakhr-al-Din and Ghiyath al-Din, built many mosques and other buildings. The members of this dynasty were great patrons of literature and the arts. By this time Herāt became known as the pearl of Khorasan". Two possible routes are therefore indicated in Figure 3, the one from Herat too, but Polo does not tell us of the town and it seems very strange that, if he passed through it, he did not mention it.

Note

A previous version was proposed in Zenodo, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3977962>

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From Sheberghan to Kashgar in the Travels of Marco Polo

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Politecnico di Torino

In a previous paper (Philica, Article 1097), we started an investigation concerning the travels of Marco Polo, using Google Earth and Wikimapia. In that article, we reconstructed the Polo's journey from Beijing to Xanadu. Here we analyze his journey from Sapurgan, today Sheberghan in Afghanistan, to Cascar, the oasis city of Kashgar in Xinjiang. In particular, we are proposing a possible way for crossing the Pamir Mountains, after Polo's words and roads, rivers and lakes displayed by Google Earth.

Keywords: Satellite Images, Google Earth, Wikimapia, Marco Polo, Afghanistan, Wakhan Corridor, Pamir Mountains, Xinjiang, China.

Introduction

The Travels of Marco Polo, or *Il Milione* in Italian, is a 13th-century book written by Rustichello da Pisa, reporting the stories told by Marco Polo while they were in prison together in Genoa. This book is describing the several travels through Asia of Polo and the period that he spent at the court of Kublai Khan [1]. In [2], some concerns about authenticity and veracity of this book are discussed, however many contents that we find in it are giving an "ultimately overwhelming probability of the broad authenticity" of the travels of Marco Polo [3].

As told in [4], an approach useful to demonstrate that Polo actually travelled from Venice to Beijing and visited the court of Kublai Kahn is that of verifying the accuracy of the itineraries described in the book. For this purpose, we can use Google Earth and Wikimapia. In [4], we studied the road to Xanadu, the Summer Capital of Kublai Khan, from Beijing, the Winter Capital of the Yuan empire. The results were so good to encourage further analyses of the travels described in the *Milione*. Here we analyze the Polo's journey from Sapurgan, today Sheberghan in Afghanistan, to Cascar, the oasis city of Kashgar in Xinjiang. In particular, we are proposing a possible way for crossing the Pamir mountains, after Polo's words and the roads, rivers and lakes displayed by Google Earth.

Henry Yule's translation (from Sapurgan to Scasem)

The journey from Sapurgan to Cascar is described after the Polo's tale of the "Old Man in the Mountain". The old man is thought to refer to Hassan-i Sabbah, Rashid ad-Din Sinan and subsequent leaders of the Assassins [5]. Let us read Polo's words of the journey in the English version given by the Scottish orientalist Sir Henry Yule (1820–1889), that we can find at the web site https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/The_Travels_of_Marco_Polo

[Concerning the City of Sapurgan] On leaving the Castle (of the Old Man), you ride over fine plains and beautiful valleys, and pretty hill-sides producing excellent grass pasture, and abundance of fruits, and all other products. ... This kind of country extends for six days' journey, with a goodly number of towns and villages, in which the people are worshippers of Mahomet. Sometimes also you meet with a tract of desert extending for 50 or 60 miles, or somewhat less, and in these deserts you find no water, but have to carry it along with you. The beasts do without drink until

you have got across the desert tract and come to watering places. So after travelling for six days as I have told you, you come to a city called SAPURGAN. It has great plenty of everything, but especially of the very best melons in the world. They preserve them by paring them round and round into strips, and drying them in the sun. When dry they are sweeter than honey, and are carried off for sale all over the country. There is also abundance of game here, both of birds and beasts.

[Of the City of Balc] BALC is a noble city and a great, though it was much greater in former days. But the Tartars and other nations have greatly ravaged and destroyed it. There were formerly many fine palaces and buildings of marble, and the ruins of them still remain. ... Now, let us quit this city, and I will tell you of another country called DOGANA. When you have quitted the city of which I have been speaking, you ride some 12 days between north-east and east, without finding any human habitation, for the people have all taken refuge in fastnesses among the mountains, on account of the Banditti and armies that harassed them. There is plenty of water on the road, and abundance of game; there are lions too. You can get no provisions on the road, and must carry with you all that you require for these 12 days.

[Of Taican, and the Mountains of Salt. Also of the Province of Casem] After those twelve days' journey you come to a fortified place called TAICAN, where there is a great corn market. It is a fine place, and the mountains that you see towards the south are all composed of salt. People from all the countries round, to some thirty days' journey, come to fetch this salt, which is the best in the world, and is so hard that it can only be broken with iron picks. 'Tis in such abundance that it would supply the whole world to the end of time. ... When you leave this town and ride three days further between north-east and east, you meet with many fine tracts full of vines and other fruits, and with a goodly number of habitations, and everything to be had very cheap. ... When you have ridden those three days, you find a town called CASEM, (Scasem in [1]) which is subject to a count. His other towns and villages are on the hills, but through this town there flows a river of some size. ... This town of Casem is at the head of a very great province, which is also called Casem. The people have a peculiar language. The peasants who keep cattle abide in the mountains, and have their dwellings in caves, which form fine and spacious houses for them, and are made with ease, as the hills are composed of earth.

Figure 1: Itinerary from Sapurgan (Shibargan, Sheberghan) to Taican (Taloqan) of about 350 km. From Balkh (Balc) to Taican, we have 210 km.

Figure 2: A possible itinerary from Taican (Taloqan) to Scasem (Keshem) and then to Eshkashem (270 km).

From Sapurgan to Scasen on Google Earth

First of all, let us show the itinerary from Sapurgan to Taican. Sapurgan is today the town of Sheberghan (Shibargan). Balc is Balkh and Taican Taloqan. The location of Dogana is unknown. It is very easy to find the road, as shown in the Figure 1. Marco Polo told of a journey of 12 days from Dogana to Taican. The travel from Balkh to Taloqan is 210 km long, which is too short for a 12 days' journey. Yule is proposing seven days (VII) instead of twelve (XII).

To find the itinerary from Taican to Scasem, the fundamental problem is to identify the last place. It is in the direction between north-east and east, "fra greco e levante" [1] of Taloqan. In this direction on the Google Earth map we find Keshem, along the Taloqan-kshem Road (50-60 km from Taloqan) (see Figure 2). After this site, we enter the Badashan, that is, the Badakhshan Province. Then, following the Kokcha River and the road along it on the map, we find also Eshkashem (Ishkashim), given in [6] as a place linked to Marco Polo's travel. But this place is too far from Taloqan, and therefore it is Keshem the Polo's Scasen, the place that we can find when we had "ridden" three days from Taloqan.

Henry Yule's translation (from Scasem to Cascar)

After leaving the town of Casem (Scasem), you ride for three days without finding a single habitation, or anything to eat or drink, so that you have to carry with you everything that you require. At the end of those three days you reach a province called Badashan, about which we shall now tell you.

[Of the Province of Badashan] Badashan is a Province inhabited by people who worship Mahomet, and have a peculiar language. It forms a very great kingdom, and the royalty is hereditary. ... It is in this province that those fine and valuable gems the Balas Rubies are found. ... There is but one special mountain that produces them, and it is called SYGHINAN. ... There is also in the same country another mountain, in which azure is found; 'tis the finest in the world, and is got in a vein like silver. There are also other mountains which contain a great amount of silver ore, so that the country is a very rich one; but it is also (it must be said) a very cold one. It produces numbers of excellent horses, remarkable for their speed. They are not shod at all, although constantly used in mountainous country, and on very bad roads. ... Those mountains are so lofty that 'tis a hard day's work, from morning till evening, to get to the top of them. On getting up, you find an extensive plain, with great abundance of grass and trees, and copious springs of pure

water running down through rocks and ravines. ... In this kingdom there are many strait and perilous passes, so difficult to force that the people have no fear of invasion. Their towns and villages also are on lofty hills, and in very strong positions. ...

[Of the Great River of Badashan; and Plain of Pamier] In leaving Badashan you ride twelve days between east and north-east, ascending a river that runs through land belonging to a brother of the Prince of Badashan, and containing a good many towns and villages and scattered habitations. The people are Mahometans, and valiant in war. At the end of those twelve days you come to a province of no great size, extending indeed no more than three days' journey in any direction, and this is called VOKHAN. The people worship Mahomet, and they have a peculiar language. ... And when you leave this little country, and ride three days north-east, always among mountains, you get to such a height that 'tis said to be the highest place in the world! And when you have got to this height you find [a great lake between two mountains, and out of it] a fine river running through a plain clothed with the finest pasture in the world; insomuch that a lean beast there will fatten to your heart's content in ten days. There are great numbers of all kinds of wild beasts; among others, wild sheep of great size, whose horns are good six palms in length. From these horns the shepherds make great bowls to eat from, and they use the horns also to enclose folds for their cattle at night. [Messer Marco was told also that the wolves were numerous, and killed many of those wild sheep. Hence quantities of their horns and bones were found, and these were made into great heaps by the way-side, in order to guide travellers when snow was on the ground.] The plain is called PAMIER, and you ride across it for twelve days together, finding nothing but a desert without habitations or any green thing, so that travellers are obliged to carry with them whatever they have need of. The region is so lofty and cold that you do not even see any birds flying. And I must notice also that because of this great cold, fire does not burn so brightly, nor give out so much heat as usual, nor does it cook food so effectually. ...

Figure 3: A possible itinerary followed by Marco Polo for crossing the Pamirs. The river followed from Eshkashem to the Wakhan Corridor is the Panj River.

[Of the Kingdom of Cascar] Cascar is a region lying between north-east and east, and constituted a kingdom in former days, but now it is subject to the Great Kaan. The people worship Mahommet. There are a good number of towns and villages, but the greatest and finest is Cascar itself. ... The people of the country have a peculiar language, and the territory extends for five days' journey.

From Scasen to Cascar on Google Earth

The itinerary proposed in the Figure 2 is following the roads that we find in Google Earth, and also the Kokcha River. Here the list of some places we have along the itinerary: Taloqan, Taloqan-kshem Rd, Astana Tapa, Kalafgan, Keshem (Scasen), Bala Jari, Barlas, Nar Darrah, Kokcha River, Feyzabad, Kokcha River, Zebak, Saricha Road, Bazgir, Eshkashem Rd, Eshkashem. From this place, it starts the most difficult part of the travel to be shown on Google Earth. However, Polo gives the references to a large river, to the Vokhan province and to a large lake between two mountains, and a river out of it, and we can use his words. And then an itinerary is given as in the Figure 3.

Before proposing the itinerary, let us read again the Polo's words: "in leaving Badashan you ride twelve days between east and north-east, ascending a river". Therefore the title of the chapter "Of the Great River of Badashan" was not the proper one. In fact, Polo is describing not the Kokcha River, which is flowing in Badashan, but a river that he found after leaving this province. Actually, after leaving the Badakhshan we find Eshkashem and, flowing through this place, the Panj river which is running between east and north-east (as precisely stated by Polo). Following this river, we arrive to a road bringing to the Wakhan Corridor. Henry Yule tells that Polo passed in this corridor, that he is mentioning as the VOKHAN country.

Therefore let us continue passing in the Wakhan Corridor. The itinerary is the following: Eshkashem, (Panj River) Qazi Deh and Yamit, Khandud, Ab Garch, Gaz Khun, (end of the path between east and north-east along the river), Pur Sang, Rachiv, Khargush, (Wakhan Corridor), Ab Gach, Sast, other places, Baza'l Gonbad, Chakmaktin Kul (great lake between two mountains), Besh Utek Kol river, Kyzylrabot, Tokhtamysh, G314 National Rd, large lake, Bulunkou Su Puketi, G314, Kashgar. Let us stress that Polo is describing a great lake between two mountains, probably the Chakmaktin Kul.

As we have seen, using the details given by Marco Polo, and the maps of Google Earth, we can imagine an itinerary of his travels. In a forthcoming article, we will show the itinerary from Kashgar to Xanadu, the Summer Capital of Kublai Khan. It seems that Marco Polo moved towards this capital when he left the Taklamakan desert.

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From Kashgar to Xanadu in the Travels of Marco Polo

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Politecnico di Torino

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Abstract: In two previous papers (Philica, 2017, Articles 1097 and 1100), we investigated the travels of Marco Polo, using Google Earth and Wikimapia. We reconstructed the Polo's travel from Beijing to Xanadu and from Sheberghan to Kashgar. Here we continue the analysis of this travel from today Kashgar to Xanadu.

Keywords: Satellite Images, Google Earth, Wikimapia, Marco Polo, Taklamakan, Southwest Xinjiang, Lop Desert, Xanadu, Marco Polo, China.

The Travels of Marco Polo is a 13th-century book written by Rustichello da Pisa, reporting the stories told by Marco to Rustichello while they were in prison together in Genoa. This book is describing the several travels through Asia of Polo and the period that he spent at the court of Kublai Khan [1]. We can read Polo's words in the English version given by the Scottish orientalist Sir Henry Yule (1820–1889), at web site https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/The_Travels_of_Marco_Polo . In [2], some concerns are discussed about authenticity and veracity of the travels described in Rustichello's book, however many contents that we can find in it are giving an "ultimately overwhelming probability of the broad authenticity" of the travels of Marco Polo [3].

As told in [4], an approach useful to demonstrate that Polo actually travelled from Venice to Beijing and visited the court of Kublai Kahn is that of verifying the accuracy of the itineraries described in the book. For this purpose, we can use Google Earth and Wikimapia. In [4], we studied the road to Xanadu, the Summer Capital of Kublai Khan, from Beijing, the Winter Capital of the Yuan empire. The results were so good to encourage further analyses of the travels of Marco Polo. In [5], we analysed the travel from Sapurgan, today Sheberghan in Afghanistan, to Cascar, the oasis city of Kashgar in Xinjiang. In particular, we proposed a possible way for crossing the Pamir mountains, after Polo's words and the roads, rivers and lakes displayed by Google Earth. In [5], we told that "in a forthcoming article, we will show the itinerary from Kashgar to Xanadu, the Summer Capital of Kublai Khan. It seems that Marco Polo moved towards this capital when he left the Taklamakan desert".

Thanks to Google Earth and Wikimapia, we can try to perform this task. Let us read Polo's words in [1], and continue the travel from Kashgar to Xanadu. We propose a possible itinerary; its rule is to follow water and trading routes, besides the names of the places given by Polo of course. Let us note that from Calacian to Tenduc, Polo is giving poor information, therefore some possible places are guessed.

Here in the following, the screenshots of the itinerary that I prepared in 2017 are given, with the aim of helping and stimulating further studies on the subject.

Figure 1: From Cascar to Ciarcian (names of places are given as in [1] too).

Figure 2: From Ciarcian to the Lop Desert.

Figure 3: From the Lop Desert to Campciu.

Figure 4: From Campciu to Calacian.

Figure 5: From Calacian to Tenduc.

Figure 6: From Tenduc to Xanadu.

Figure 7: Detail of the road from Sindaciu to Xanadu, made by means of the fundamental help of Google Earth and Wikimapia.

In the travel to reach Xanadu, Marco Polo followed a branch of the Silk Road. The Silk Road consisted of several routes. From the ancient commercial centers of China, the overland intercontinental Silk Road divided into northern and southern routes bypassing the Taklimakan Desert and Lop Nur. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Silk_Road . Polo used the southern route. The travel from Kashgar to Ciarcian is quite clear, because is it fixed by the local environment. Some references can help us in finding the places on the maps from the travel from Ciarcian to Xanadu. Of course, first of all, there are the words written by Rustichello [1], about the route to reach the palace of Giandu, that is Xanadu.

Ciarcian is the modern Qiemo, or Qarqan in Uighur. Qiemo is a county in the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region of the People's Republic of China, bordering the Tibet Autonomous Region to the south. The county seat is at Qiemo Town. en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qiemo_County

Stephen Haw tells, in his book [6], that **Ciarcian** or Qiemo is on the Charchan River. "Below Qiemo, the course of this river turns to run roughly east-north-east for a considerable distance. The bed is often dry from a short distance beyond Qiemo, but there would usually be water below the surface of the land. This would make it reasonably easy to follow the river valley until it finally loses itself in the desert" [6]. In the book [6], "Marco Polo's China: A Venetian in the Realm of Khubilai Khan", Stephen Haw re-examines Marco Polo's book, arguing convincingly that he did indeed go to China. The book concludes that Marco Polo's work is an accurate, important and useful source for an extraordinary period of Chinese history.

Then, let us use Google Maps, and there we can see clearly the river, connecting Charchan to Loubuzhuang. After Ciarcian, Polo is mentioning Lop. "**Lop** is Lob or Luobuzhuang, which still exists north of modern Ruoqiang (Charklikh), more or less exactly where the course of the Charchan River becomes indistinct. It stands near the south-eastern limit of the Taklimakan Desert, where it become possible to cross the Tarim Basin from South to north by following the valleys of the Charchan and Tarim Rivers", as told in [6].

"It was recorded that the Buddhist monk Xuanzang passed through a town called Na-Fu-Bo on his way home to China in 645 CE, and Marco Polo in the 13th century passed through a place he called the town of Lop, and both of these were suggested by Aurel Stein to be Charklik. Stein indicated that there is "conclusive evidence" that Charklik was already the chief centre of the region when Xuanzang passed through the town". From item on the Kingdom of Charklik en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kingdom_of_Charklik .

Rustichello tells that "va una città ch'è nome Sachion, che è a lo Grande Cane. La provincia si chiama Tangut; La terra è tra levante e greco. Quegli dagl'idoli àno per loro speciale favella; no sono mercatanti, ma vivono di terra". **Saciu** (Sachiu, Sachion) is Shazhou, now Dunhuang in the far north-west of Gansu province. "The old town was on the western side of the modern one. Remains of its walls, made of compacted earth, can still be seen today. The name Shazhou was applied to the town and the district is governed early in the seventh century, under the Tang Dynasty. After about the middle of the eight century, it came under Tibetan control. Later, it formed part of the Gansu Uighur state and then of the Xi Xia kngdom. It was officially named Shazhou again in 1277 and become the seat of a lu three years later. Marco notes that there were many Buddhist temples and monasteries there. Dunhuang is famous today for the Mogao cave-temples near the town. Tangut is Xi Xia". From [6]. After Saciu, Polo found **Succiu**, which is SUCHOW, Suzhou, now Jiuquan. Formerly, 'Su' was pronounced 'Suk' or 'Siuk' [6].

About Ca(n)picion (Campiciu, **Campciu** in Tangut, KANCHOW, 38.9342,100.4520, ZHANGYE), we have information from [7], "Marco Polo's Asia", by Leonardo Olschki, University of California Press, 1960. "Canpicion è una cittade ch'è in Ta(n)gut, e è molto nobile e grande; e è capo della provincia di Tangut. La ge(n)te sono idoli, e àvi di quelli ch'adorano Malcomet, e èvi cristiani; e èvi in quella città tre chiese grandi e belle. ... Or ci partiamo di qui, e conteremovi d'altre verso tramontana. E sí vi dico che messer Niccolò e messer Mafeo e messer Marco dimorarono uno anno per loro fatti in questa terra. Ora

anderemo 60 giornate verso tramontana". Polo arrived to Sindaciu.

Tenduc and **Sindaciu**. Tenduc is a province (Tanduc, near TOQTO, KWEIHWACHENG, 40.810556, 111.65222). About these places we find information in [8] and in the notes given by the Henry Yule translation, https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/The_Travels_of_Marco_Polo. SINDATUI (Sindacui, Sindatury, Sindacin, Saindatus, Sindatur, Sindincin, ZHANGJIAKOU may be). SINDACHU (Sindacui, Suidatui, etc., of the MSS.) is SIUEN-HWA-FU, "called under the Kin Dynasty Siuen-te-chau, more than once besieged and taken by Chinghiz. It is said to have been a summer residence of the later Mongol Emperors, and fine parks full of grand trees remain on the western side. It is still a large town and the capital of department or *Fu*, about 25 miles south of the Gate on the Great Wall at Chang Kia Kau, which the Mongols and Russians call Kalgan. There is still a manufacture of felt and woollen articles here".

The city called by Polo **Ciagannor** (Chagannour, meaning in Mongol "White Lake") "is the Chaghan Balghasun mentioned by Timkowski as an old city of the Mongol era, the ruined rampart of which he passed about 30 miles north of the Great Wall at Kalgan, and some 55 miles from Siuen-hwa, adjoining the Imperial pastures. It stands near a lake still called Chaghan–Nor, and is called by the Chinese Pe-ching-tzu, or White City, a translation of Chaghan Balghasun. Dr. Bushell says of one of the lakes (Ichi–Nor), a few miles east of Chaghan–Nor: "We ... found the water black with waterfowl, which rose in dense flocks, and filled the air with discordant noises. Swans, geese, and ducks predominated, and three different species of cranes were distinguished" (from Yule's book).

About this town we read in [9], in a IUB Lectures, Meetingd and Conferences, entitled "The Chaghan Naghur Palace and Yuan Royal Falconing", by Baohai Dang. "Chaghan Na'ur (Mongolian name for White Lake) Palace was an important imperial residence of Khubilai Khan and other emperors of the Yuan Dynasty. Its site, Xiao Hong Cheng, lies on the steppe of Guyuan County, Hebei Province, on the way between Khanbaliq (Dadu) and Xanadu (Shangdu). Chaghan Na'ur Palace was developed from temporary traveling ordo (royal yurts) into a permanent royal town in the reign of Khubilai Khan. It was presumably called the Royal Town of Asigh Dabusu. In the 1980s, the palaces and Buddhist temples built there were found in an archaeological investigation. Falconry was the most popular hunting form for ancient Mongol nobles. Because of the excellent environment, Chaghan Na'ur and the surrounding areas became the biggest falconry ground of the Yuan emperors. Thousands of falconers were organized to provide service for Yuan royal falconry". Since the Chaghan Na'ur falconry was vividly narrated in The Travels of Marco Polo, Ref.9 is analysing the related description given by Polo.

"Xiao Hong Chang, which has been identifies as Chaghan Na'ur, is located in a vast meadow near the Shandian he River in Guyuan xian. A large salt lake called Hulun Naoer (i.e. Hulan Na'ur, Red Lake) lies south-west of the ruins and can be identified with the lake of Chaghan Na'ur. A summer palace called Jingming gong had been constructed by the Jin dynasty nearby (in Lianxing). Chinggis and Qubilai visited it, but it was abandoned for a new construction. According to the archaeological reports by Zheng Shaozong and Yin Zixian, Xiao Hong Cheng consisted of two walled enclosures side by side. The walls of the larger enclosure were made of blocks of reddish stone and formed a rectangle of 346 m (north-south) by 308 m (east-west)". Coordinates 41.743529, 115.758393 [10].

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The road to Xanadu in the Travels of Marco Polo

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna
Politecnico di Torino

Using Google Earth and Wikimapia, we can try to reconstruct the journey from Beijing to Xanadu described by Marco Polo in the Milione. A possible itinerary is here proposed, in agreement with the words of the Venetian traveler.

Keywords: Satellite Images, Google Earth, Wikimapia, Marco Polo, China.

Introduction

Il Milione, in English commonly known as The Travels of Marco Polo, is a 13th-century travelogue that Rustichello da Pisa wrote according to the stories told by Marco Polo, while they were in prison together in Genoa. This book is describing the Polo's travels through Asia between 1276 and 1291, and the period that he spent at the court of Kublai Khan [1]. The book was in origin written in Old French and translated into many European languages in Marco Polo's own lifetime (the original manuscripts are now lost).

Since the book is containing several fabulous stories, from the beginning of its publication it aroused some incredulity in the readers and even today some scholars are questioning whether Polo had actually travelled to China or he was just telling the stories that he heard from other travelers [2,3]. However, as economist Mark Elvin wrote in the preface of a book written by Hans Ulrich Vogel [4], Vogel has demonstrated by specific examples and discussions "the ultimately overwhelming probability of the broad authenticity" of Polo's book. It is, "in essence, authentic, and, when used with care, in broad terms to be trusted as a serious, though obviously not always final, witness." [4] The study reported in [4] is based on evidences about the description given by Marco Polo of currencies (paper and cowry money), salts and related revenues.

Another approach useful to demonstrate that Polo visited China and the court of Kublai Kahn is that of verifying the accuracy of the itineraries described in the book. For this purpose, we can use Google Earth and Wikimapia, to verify the plausibility of the words of Marco Polo. Of course, the complete analysis of the book is requiring a rather extensive work. Here we limit ourselves to the itinerary followed by Kublai Khan for moving from Xanadu, the Summer Capital, to Beijing, the Winter Capital. Let us remember that Kublai reigned from 1260 to 1294. In 1271, he established the Yuan dynasty in China, ruling as the first Yuan emperor until his death. From the discussion, we will see that, for determining the path on which the Khan moved, Wikimapia is an excellent source of information. A possible itinerary is here proposed, mapped on Google Earth. This itinerary is also compared to the roads that today are crossing the region.

Henry Yule's translation

First of all, let us read Polo's words in the English version given by the Scottish orientalist Sir Henry Yule (1820-1889), that we can find at the web site https://en.wikisource.org/wiki/The_Travels_of_Marco_Polo

[Concerning the Province of Tenduc, and the Descendants of Prester John]: ... All this region is subject to the Great Kaan. There is a city you come to called SINDACHU (Sindaciu in Italian), where they carry on a great many crafts such as provide for the equipment of the Emperor's troops. In a mountain of the province there is a very good silver mine, from which much silver is got: the place is called YDIFU. The country is well stocked with game, both beast and bird. Now we will quit that province and go three days' journey forward.

[Concerning the Kaan's Palace of Chagannor (Ciagannor in Italian)]: At the end of those three days you find a city called CHAGAN NOR [which is as much as to say White Pool], at which

there is a great Palace of the Grand Kaan's; and he likes much to reside there on account of the Lakes and Rivers in the neighbourhood, which are the haunt of swans, and of a great variety of other birds. ...

[Of the City of Chandu, and the Kaan's Palace There] And when you have ridden three days from the city last mentioned, between north-east and north, you come to a city called CHANDU (Ciandu, also known as Xanadu), which was built by the Kaan now reigning. There is at this place a very fine marble Palace, the rooms of which are all gilt and painted with figures of men and beasts and birds, and with a variety of trees and flowers, all executed with such exquisite art that you regard them with delight and astonishment. Round this Palace a wall is built, inclosing a compass of 16 miles, and inside the Park there are fountains and rivers and brooks, and beautiful meadows, with all kinds of wild animals (excluding such as are of ferocious nature), which the Emperor has procured and placed there to supply food for his gyrfalcons and hawks, which he keeps there in mew. Of these there are more than 200 gyrfalcons alone, without reckoning the other hawks. The Kaan himself goes every week to see his birds sitting in mew, and sometimes he rides through the park with a leopard behind him on his horse's croup; and then if he sees any animal that takes his fancy, he slips his leopard at it, and the game when taken is made over to feed the hawks in mew. This he does for diversion.

Moreover [at a spot in the Park where there is a charming wood] he has another Palace built of cane, of which I must give you a description. ... In short, the whole Palace is built of these canes, which (I may mention) serve also for a great variety of other useful purposes. The construction of the Palace is so devised that it can be taken down and put up again with great celerity; and it can all be taken to pieces and removed whithersoever the Emperor may command. When erected, it is braced [against mishaps from the wind] by more than 200 cords of silk. The Lord abides at this Park of his, dwelling sometimes in the Marble Palace and sometimes in the Cane Palace for three months of the year, to wit, June, July, and August; preferring this residence because it is by no means hot; in fact it is a very cool place. When the 28th day of [the Moon of] August arrives he takes his departure, and the Cane Palace is taken to pieces. ...

Henry Yule's notes

In his notes to the text, Yule tells that there were two roads to go from Beijing to Xanadu: "the eastern road through Tu-shi-k'ow", and the western that was used for the return journey. Marco Polo took this last road, "which ran from Peking to Siuen-te chau through the same places as now; but from the latter town it led, not to Kalgan as it does now, but more to the west, to a place called now Shan-fang pu where the pass across the Ye-hu ling range begins". "On both these roads nabo, or temporary palaces, were built, as resting-places for the Khans; eighteen on the eastern road, and twenty-four on the western." This was asserted by Palladius, that is Pyotr Ivanovich Kafarov, (1817,1878), who wrote "Elucidations of the Marco Polo's Travels in North-China", 1876. The same author makes the following remarks: "M. Polo's statement that he travelled three days from Siuen-te chau to Chagannor, and three days also from the latter place to Shang-tu, agrees with the information contained in the 'Researches on the Routes to Shangtu.' The Chinese authors have not given the precise position of Lake Chagannor; there are several lakes in the desert on the road to Shangtu, and their names have changed with time. The palace in Chagannor was built in 1280".

"Chandu, called more correctly in Ramusio (Giovanni Battista Ramusio, 1485-1557, Italian geographer and travel writer) Xandu, i.e. SHANDU, or "Upper Court," the Chinese title of Kublai's summer residence at Kaipingfu, Mongolice Keibung", is called also Loan king, i.e. "the capital on the Loan River," according to Palladius. Yule tells us that the ruins "still exist, in about lat. 40 deg. 22', and a little west of the longitude of Peking". He continues also telling that the site is "118 miles in direct line from Chaghan-nor, making Polo's three marches into rides of unusual length". The ruins bear the Mongol name of Chao Naiman Sume Khotan, meaning 'city of the 108 temples,' and are about 26 miles to the north-west of Dolon-nor, a bustling, dirty town of modern origin, famous for the manufactory of idols, bells, and other ecclesiastical paraphernalia of Buddhism. The site was visited (though not described) by Pere Gerbillon in 1691, and since then by no European traveller till 1872, when Dr. Bushell of the British Legation at Peking, and the Hon. T. G. Grosvenor, made a journey thither from the capital, by way of the Nan-kau Pass, Kalgan, and the vicinity of Chaghan-nor, the route that would seem to have been habitually followed, in their annual migration, by Kublai and his successors".

Here a part of the description of Xanadu given by Yule in his notes. "The walls, of earth faced with brick and unhewn stone, still stand, forming, as in the Tartar city of Peking, a double enceinte, of which the inner line no doubt represents the area of the "Marble Palace" of which Polo speaks. This forms a square of about 2 li (2/3 of a mile) to the side, and has three gates-south, east, and west, of which the southern one still stands intact, a perfect arch, 20 ft. high and 12 ft. wide. The outer wall forms a square of 4 li (1-1/3 mile) to the side, and has six gates. The foundations of temples and palace-buildings can be traced, and both enclosures are abundantly strewn with blocks of marble and fragments of lions, dragons, and other sculptures, testifying to the former existence of a flourishing city, but exhibiting now scarcely one stone upon another. ... This city occupies the south-east angle of a more extensive enclosure, bounded by what is now a grassy mound, and embracing, on Dr. Bushell's estimate, about 5 square miles. Further knowledge may explain the discrepancy from Marco's dimension, but this must be the park of which he speaks".

It is very interesting what Yule is also reporting. "Between the year of the Rat (1264), when Kublai was fifty years old, and the year of the Sheep (1271), in the space of eight years, he built four great cities, viz. for Summer Residence SHANGTU KEIBUNG Kuerdu Balgasun, for Winter Residence Yeke DAITU Khotan, and on the shady side of the Altai Arulun TSAGHAN BALGASUN, and Erchuegin LANGTING Balgasun. ... A valuable letter from Dr. Bushell - tells Yule - enables me now to indicate the position of Langtin: The district through which the river flows eastward from Shangtu is known to the Mongolians of the present day by the name of Lang-tirh (Lang-ting'rh).... The ruins of the city are marked on a Chinese map in my possession Pai-dseng-tzu, i.e. 'White City,' implying that it was formerly an Imperial residence. The remains of the wall are 7 or 8 li in diameter, of stone, and situated about 40 li north-north-west from Dolon-nor."

A possible itinerary

The discussion given by Yule is very detailed. The problem is that the names of the locations are not easily found on the modern maps. For instance, of the two roads to go from Beijing to Xanadu, I was not able to find "the eastern road through Tu-shi-k'ow". So let us concentrate on the western road. In particular, let us consider the Polo's main sites Sindaciu, Ciagannor and Chandu and locate them on a Google Earth map. Today, Sindaciu is Xuanhua [5]. For Ciagannor, we can use [6]. In this reference it is told that "Xian Hong Cheng, which has been identified as Chagan Na'ur, is located in a vast meadow near the Shandian he River in Guyan xian". A large salt lake called Hulun Naoer lies south-west of the ruins and can be identified with the lake of Chagan Na'ur. "A summer palace called Jingming gong had been constructed by the Jin dynasty nearby (in Liangxing)".

The place of Chagan Na'ur can be easily found using Wikimapia at the coordinates: 41°44'26"N 115°44'58"E. In Wikimapia, it is described in the following way:

小宏城遗址 小宏城遗址是一座距今750多年的草原废城，又称小红城，亦名乌兰城，即元世祖忽必烈察罕淖儿行宫，坐落于河北省沽源县闪电河西岸。小宏城遗址规模宏大，内容丰富，总体分为三期建筑。在小宏城西南500米处，是一片面积约1200平方米的古建筑遗址，裸露地表的有整块的筒瓦、青砖，有笼制花纹黑釉瓷缸、绿釉大瓷缸、鸡腿瓶和不少泥质灰陶、白瓷器残片。Archeological site, Nearby cities: 乌兰察布市, 锡林浩特市, 赤峰市

That is, using a Google translation, " Hongcheng ruins, Hongcheng is a 750 years old town in the the grassland waste city, also known as Red City, or Wulan City, that is, the ancestors of Kublai Khan Nao Nao children palace, located in Hebei Province Guyuan County". The rest of the Chinese text is not enough clear in the Google translation. Another town that we can easily find is Kalgan as told in <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zhangjiakou>. In the Figure 1, we give a map prepared using Wikimapia and Google Earth, showing all the places that we were able to identify and others reported by Wikimapia. On the map we are proposing (in red) the possible itinerary followed by Marco Polo from Beijing to Xanadu.

Figure 1: A possible itinerary from Beijing to Xanadu, here proposed after the description of Marco Polo and the notes of Yule.

It seems that Yule, following Palladius, considered Polo moving from Sindaciu to Ciagannor, in a "three days' journey". As we can see from a Google Earth map (Figure 1), the travel moving on the red itinerary from Sindaciu to Ciagannor is of about 160 km, so the journey would be of 50-55 km per day, which seems quite hard to do at Polo's time. However, let us read again Polo's words "Now we will quit that province and go three days' journey forward". The journey described by Polo is from the province, not from the town. Therefore, the travel was shorter: in my opinion, the "three days' journey" is from a gate of the Great Wall, probably the border of the province, marked with A in the Figure 2. From this place A to Ciagannor (B), a three days' journey is more plausible. Then, "when you have ridden three days from the city last mentioned, between north-east and north, you come to a city called CHANDU". Xanadu is C in

the Figure 2. From the map, we can see that the journey from A to B, and that from B to C are comparable. Therefore, it is possible that Marco Polo was describing the journey from a gate of the Great Wall to Ciagannor, and not from Sindaciu to Ciagannor. Let us also note that, measuring with Google Earth the distance between Ciagannor and Xanadu, we find about 80 km, not the mentioned "118 miles", that in the Yule's notes are "making Polo's three marches into rides of unusual length".

Figure 2: The itinerary from Beijing to Xanadu, as proposed in the Figure 1, on a map which is showing modern roads and the fortifications of the Great Wall too (Courtesy Google Earth). A is a gate of the Wall, which is shown by the yellow square markers. We consider A as the starting point of the three days' journey to Ciagannor (B) described by Marco Polo.

In preparing the Figures 1 and 2 we have also considered Yule's note telling that Marco Polo took the road, "which ran from Peking to Siuen-te chau through the same places as now; but from the latter town it led, not to Kalgan as it does now, but more to the west, to a place called now Shan-fang pu where the pass across the Ye-hu ling range begins". Again, it is difficult to locate Shan-fang pu, but observing the Google Earth map we can imagine a journey passing in the valley where we find the Wanquan Fortress (Wikimapia) (see the Figure 3).

Figure 3: In preparing the itinerary we have also considered Yule’s note telling that Marco Polo took the road which ran from Beijing to Sindaciu “through the same places as now; but from the latter town it led, not to Kalgan as it does now, but more to the west”. Observing the Google Earth map we can imagine a journey passing in the valley where we find the Wanquan Fortress (Wikimapia) and also the modern highway (G207) crossing the mountain range. Let us note that passing through Kalgan we have the eastern (S242) road.

Comparing the red itinerary to the modern roads, we can see that, after crossing the mountain range, the ancient travelers moved on a Eastern path, passing through many towns which today are in ruins. Then, besides the investigation of possible itineraries, the Polo’s book can also stimulate the study of the ancient towns and fortresses of China using Google Earth and Wikimapia. We discussed in [7-9] of Xanadu, which is quite interesting for its remarkable planning. Of the other towns mentioned by Polo or evidenced by Wikimapia, we will discuss in a future work.

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